

THE IMPACT OF ELECTRONIC MEDIA ON OUR LIFE

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Abstract: As media is moving in to twenty-first century and the way of doing business and marketing has changed, researcher's studies focus on Electronic Media meaning as a promotional tool and how it Effects on consumer behavior and observations. Through internet, Electronic Media allows public to access information and ideas quickly and usefully. The aim of this article is to analyze Electronic Media importance and prepare classification of E-media. A literature review comparison method will be used at the end of this article.

Keywords: Elektronik media, Media communication, Electronic media evolution.

Electronic media has transformed the way people communicate. With the advent of smartphones, individuals can stay connected 24/7, breaking down barriers of time and distance. Social media platforms have facilitated the exchange of ideas and information on a global scale, fostering virtual communities and bringing together like-minded individuals from diverse backgrounds. The internet has democratized access to information. Now, anyone with an internet connection can access a vast repository of knowledge on various subjects. News and information can spread rapidly through social media, enabling real-time updates on events and issues from around the world. Television and streaming services have transformed the entertainment industry, allowing consumers to access a wide range of content on-demand. The shift from traditional cable TV to Over-the-Top (OTT) platforms has given viewers greater control over their viewing preferences.

Electronic media has facilitated cultural exchange and globalization. Audiences from different parts of the world can now access content from various cultures, leading to a blending of ideas, values, and traditions. This has both positive and negative effects, as it can promote cross-cultural understanding or lead to cultural homogenization. The speed and ease of sharing information on the internet have led to the proliferation of misinformation and fake news. In the era of social media, it can be challenging to distinguish between reliable sources and dubious ones, leading to the spread of false information.

The digitization of personal information raises significant privacy and security concerns. Data breaches, identity theft, and cyberattacks are becoming increasingly common, necessitating robust measures to protect users' data and digital identities. Despite the widespread adoption of electronic media, there is still a digital divide that hinders access to information and opportunities for many individuals, particularly in developing regions. Bridging this gap is crucial for promoting digital inclusion and ensuring equal access to educational and economic resources.

According to (Strauss, 2016), Electronic Media is defined as “the use of Electronic Media and applications for planning then executing the distribution and the pricing and to create transactions that fulfil invidious and company’s goals”. Reviewing many related articles, the term Electronic Media is responsible for such big change in technology and made a big social effect. Many opportunities for individuals and companies are provided. Individuals can purchase a wide variety of services and goods. In one hand, Electronic Media is a door for consumers to select then buy definitely and freely. In the other hand, companies expand their markets and introduce new services and product with a big competition in global environments (Dennis, 2008) for many reasons:

- Electronic media build relationships between people and provides opportunities to share interests, goods and services.
- Electronic Media socialize the media communication in an open and connected market.

- Electronic Media represents how people can share information and provide users with new form of empowerment sharing.
- Thru Electronic Media (EM), people are able to communicate online and exchange without limits.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Electronic media is used as a competitive advantage tool and increase efficiency in media. It shows social media is effective even if it is relatively new to the media world, it is just as useful and effective if not more than other traditional forms of media. Top managers have to understand that there has been a shift of power from the producers to the consumers. Moreover, electronic media provides a platform for consumers to speak their thoughts regarding a new advertisement, products or service. Many researchers concluded by stating that the business world is developing rapidly and that with the constant communication that has been made available marketers have been given the big chance to have the potential consumers, and at the same time keeping and getting the loyalty from present consumers.

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